

Influence of Environmental Variables on Carbon Mineralization in Diverse Soil Management Systems Under Maize Cropping in Kwara State, Nigeria

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Received: 20 December 2021

Accepted: 23 March 2022

Abstract

Understanding the influence of agricultural soil management practices on soil processes and the environment is vital for sustainable food production. Therefore, this study evaluated the impact of soil temperature and moisture on soil organic carbon mineralisation under synthetic (NPK) and organic (biochar) amendments in a maize cropping system in Ilorin, Southern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. The objectives were to determine the C mineralisation and C sequestering potential under each amendment and assess how precipitation amounts and soil temperature influence carbon mineralisation. Two soil types (Anthrodentic Ustorthent and Typic Ustorthent) were used, and four treatments (control, NPK, biochar+NPK, and biochar) replicated thrice were laid out in completely randomised design on each soil. Soil respiration was measured in-situ by the alkali absorption method. Data collected was subjected to analysis of variance procedure for complete randomized design to determine significant differences in treatment means, correlation and regression analyses were also carried out to test the relationships amongst experimental factors and variable responses. Results showed that evaluated nutrient management options did not significantly influence C mineralisation. C mineralisation, however, differed between soils, with Typic Ustorthent having higher organic carbon (OC), total CO₂ emission (82.35 mg) and mean CO₂ emission rates (1.18 mg m⁻² d⁻¹). Correlation analysis showed differing relationships between soil temperature and C mineralisation under the different treatments and soils, with significant positive correlation ($r=0.44$; $p \leq 0.05$) recorded only under sole biochar treatment in the Typic Ustorthent. Rainfall amounts had no significant correlation with C mineralisation.

Keywords: C mineralisation, C sequestration, Entisols, rainfall, temperature, SOC

Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) plays an essential role in the stability and fertility of soils (Trivedi *et al.*, 2018) and exists in inorganic and organic forms. Soil C plays a crucial role in the terrestrial carbon cycle, releases nutrients for plant growth, promotes soil structure, biological and physical health, and is a buffer against harmful substances. These make maintaining optimum amounts of OC in soil paramount for sustainable agricultural production.

Land management options present opportunities for good agricultural soil resource use, sustainable food production and sustenance of livelihoods. In this regard, optimum soil management under crop production is desirable for good yield and minimised adverse environmental effects. Previous studies have shown that land management is closely linked to SOC turnover (Jamala and Oke, 2013; Xiao *et al.*, 2017), which has a far-reaching impact on terrestrial carbon cycles and connected ecological implications such as climate change.

In an earlier study, Vanden *et al.* (2003) showed that SOC content is lost principally in the form of CO₂, following the conversion of natural land states for agricultural use. However, carbon-enhancing land management helps improve the carbon sink potential of soils (Ding *et al.*, 2014). , the C sink or source potential of soil thus depends on soil physical and chemical factors influenced by land management, which impact soil functions and affect the activities of soil microbial populations that decompose SOM and make the nutrients available to plants (Guo *et al.*, 2017).

Climatic variables are another critical set of factors determining C turnover in soil. Research has shown that soil temperature and moisture affect microbial activity, surface runoff, land surface energy dynamics, root zone productivity, and biomass yield (Hacki *et al.*, 2005), all of which bear C turnover in soil. Soil water also enhance dissolved organic carbon (DOC) leaching from the forest floor, a vital C pool. Temperature and precipitation are dominant factors affecting soil organic carbon storage (Herold *et al.*, 2014).

Understanding the interaction between climatic factors and management options is thus important to design tailored land management approaches that guarantee increased food production and SOC buildup. This is especially important under maize production due to its centrality as one of the world's most important food/ feed and industrial use crops. Therefore, this study is designed to assess the effect of variable nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium compound fertilisers application rates and biochar amendment under conventional tillage practices for their C sequestration potential.

Low nutrient content and accelerated mineralisation of SOM remain two significant constraints facing sustainable agriculture, as earlier identified by Renner (2007). In the face of high human population growth, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, intensified agricultural management has become inevitable. This reality makes studies aimed at optimising land management under prevailing climatic conditions pertinent. We hypothesise that biochar addition will lower SOC mineralisation, and N fertilisation will increase C mineralisation in the test soils.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study area

This study was carried out within the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm in Ilorin, Kwara State, in Southern Guinea Savannah (SGS) agroecological zone of

Nigeria (Figure 1). Geographically, the state is located between latitudes $7^{\circ} 45'$ and $9^{\circ} 30'$ North of the Equator and Longitudes $2^{\circ} 30'$ and $6^{\circ} 25'$ East of the Prime meridian. The SGS zone has a mean annual rainfall of 100–150 cm and a wet season lasting 6–8 months between March and October (Table 1).

The climate is tropical and is characterised by double rainfall maxima tropical wet and dry weather. Temperature is uniformly high and ranges between 25°C and 30°C in the wet season, and dry season temperature ranges between 33°C and 34°C . Relative humidity in the wet season is between 75 to 80 %, while about 65 % in the dry season.

Fig. 1: Map showing the study area and experimental locations

The state is considered one of the essential rainfed agricultural areas in semi-arid regions of the country and could be defined as dependent mainly on rainfall for crop production. Food crops produced are mostly maize, rice, sorghum, yam, cassava, water yam and sweet potato, which constitute the main staple foods (Ajadi *et al.*, 2011). To a lower extent, the soils are formed majorly from basement complex rocks (metamorphic and igneous rocks) and sedimentary rocks. The metamorphic rocks include biotite gneiss, banded gneiss, quartzite augite gneiss and granitic gneiss. The intrusive rock includes pegmatite and vein quartz (Olaniyan and Ogunkunle, 2007).

Table 1. 1989 – 2014 monthly rainfall data for Ilorin (Source: Ilorin airport meteorological station)

Years	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
1989	0.0	0.0	56.2	96.5	106.8	239.9	111.3	199.9	233.8	188.9	0.0	0.0	1233.4
1990	0.0	8.5	0.0	158.2	130.7	129.7	150.0	116.8	225.1	98.7	17.4	0.0	1035.1
1991	17.2	17.6	37.8	67.5	340.8	135.9	9.0	138.8	124.8	127.0	0.0	0.0	1326.7
1992	0.0	0.0	2.0	46.7	166.6	90.1	134.7	75.9	129.4	193.2	0.0	0.0	838.6
1993	0.0	102.5	79.0	35.2	176.1	220.6	100.4	333.6	362.8	84.9	0.0	0.0	1495.0
1994	70.1	0.0	7.9	161.0	168.0	168.1	283.1	83.4	201.0	317.9	289.9	0.0	1750.4
1995	0.0	0.0	79.0	79.0	234.0	186.5	140.5	245.1	272.5	133.0	11.5	12.0	1393.1
1996	0.0	0.0	56.5	67.1	165.3	154.2	96.4	154.6	199.8	96.3	0.0	0.0	990.2
1997	0.0	0.0	93.1	206.4	207.4	375.2	158.8	107.6	224.4	115.3	15.0	0.0	1503.2
1998	0.0	0.8	17.1	73.9	159.6	132.3	58.5	170.9	224.8	140.0	0.0	0.0	977.9
1999	0.0	32.5	54.9	67.1	143.3	244.9	195.6	85.7	265.6	182.5	22.8	0.0	1294.9
2000	0.0	2.2	2.4	22.8	68.2	262.2	93.4	163.9	268.0	9.0	0.0	0.0	892.1
2001	0.0	0.0	18.0	45.0	139.0	121.8	138.7	44.5	176.4	60.8	0.0	0.0	744.2
2002	0.0	0.0	59.4	163.2	57.2	97.8	180.8	182.7	144.5	176.7	6.5	0.0	1068.8
2003	0.0	14.0	12.4	93.9	124.5	360.7	123.2	130.9	176.2	133.4	46.7	0.0	1215.9
2004	18.2	33.1	4.0	67.0	260.5	159.2	211.4	145.4	243.5	98.1	31.6	0.0	1272.0
2005	0.0	5.5	25.5	75.7	187.6	171.0	130.2	93.6	282.6	109.8	10.5	0.0	1092.0
2006	1.2	16.1	27.5	106.6	163.7	259.6	224.1	88.2	276.2	190.0	0.0	0.0	1353.2
2007	0.0	7.0	22.0	115.0	306.2	227.7	205.3	189.9	236.2	162.5	0.0	2.5	1474.3
2008	0.0	0.0	9.5	123.5	35.2	184.1	394.1	329.5	343.6	88.6	3.4	5.2	1516.7
2009	6.0	0.5	19.6	219.2	112.1	170.6	249.5	226.0	231.0	112.0	47.4	0.0	1393.9
2010	0.0	6.5	60.9	58.2	112.2	45.1	139.1	123.7	228.3	226.4	2.0	0.0	1002.4
2011	0.0	19.1	4.8	13.5	169.1	231.8	220.2	294.5	334.6	163.2	0.0	0.0	1450.8
2012	26.0	0.0	0.6	173.3	205.7	162.8	202.6	168.1	200.8	84.4	0.0	7.2	1231.5
2013	0.5	39.0	39.8	181.8	81.8	132.9	107.3	17.7	202.5	154.3	0.0	11.4	969.0
2014	6.3	34.2	71.0	321.4	163.8	154.7	82.1	94.9	391.6	259.4	0.0	0.0	1579.4
MEAN	5.6	13.0	33.1	109.2	161.0	185.4	159.2	154.1	238.5	142.6	19.4	1.5	1234.4

Soil Survey

A free soil survey identified two soil types within the study area. Profile pits were dug and described, following United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Soil Survey Staff guidelines (2017). Soil classification was done following USDA Soil Survey Staff (2014) guidelines. Identified soils were labelled UTRF 1 and UTRF 2 at approximately 8°27'48.91"N 4°39'37.01"E and 8°27'21.76"N 4°39'51.53"E respectively. The soils were classified as Anthrodensic Ustorthent and Typic Ustorthent, respectively, based on observed morphological and measured physical and chemical properties.

Laboratory Analysis

Top (0 – 130 cm) and profile horizons soil samples were air-dried, 2 mm sieved, and subjected to physical and chemical analyses following procedures outlined in Table 2. The biochar was made out of hardwood in a top-lit updraft kiln at ~350 °C. Biochar samples were broken, ground (using a ceramic mortar and pestle) and passed through a 0.5 mm sieve mesh before analyses. Analyses procedures are presented in Table 2. The soils' morphological, physical and chemical properties are shown in Tables 3 and 4, respectively, and biochar properties in Table 5.

Table 2. *Methods of soil and biochar samples analyses*

Parameter	Method of Analyses	
	Soil	Biochar
Soil particle size fractions	Gee and Or, 2002	
pH	Thomas (1996)	In 0.1 N KCl solution (1:10 wt/wt) ratio
Total Nitrogen	Bremner, 1996	Enders and Lehmann (2012)
Organic carbon	Walkley and Black, 1934	Enders and Lehmann (2012)
Available phosphorus (Bray 1-P):	Bray and Kurtz (1945)	Enders and Lehmann (2012)
Exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K, and Na)	1 N ammonium acetate (NH ₄ OAc) extraction	Enders and Lehmann (2012)
ECEC	Juo et al. (1976)	
Exchangeable acidity	Peech et al., 1962	
Percentage base saturation	Summation of total exchangeable bases expressed as a percentage of CEC	
Moisture content		ASTM E871-82
Volatile matter		ASTM E871-82
Ash		ASTM E871-82
Fixed carbon		ASTM E871-82

Table 3. Morphological properties of soil profile pit horizons

Pedon	Horizon designation	Depth (cm)	Colour (moist)	Texture +	Structure ++	Mottles +++	Drainage ***	Boundary **	Consistence *	Artifacts ^	Roots ^v	Landform/topography
UTRF1	Ap	0-20	10 YR 2/2 (very dark brown)	I	Mo, vs.sab	N	III	d,s	m,lo;w,nst,npl	A	C co	Undulating
	B ₁	20-40	10 YR 5/4 (yellowish brown)	fs	Mo,me,sab	N	III	d,s	m,lo; w,ssp	A	C,md	
	B ₂	40-60	10 YR 4/4 (dark yellowish brown)	g,cl	Mo,me,ab	N	III	d,s	m, fr.;w,ssp	A	F,co	
	Bv	60-115	2.5YR 4/8 (red)	g,cl	Mo,me,ab	N	III	d,s	m,lo;w,ssp	A	F,vfi	
UTRF2	Ap	0-10	10 YR 4/3 (brown)	I	Mo, vf,sab	N	III	d,b	m,lo;w,ssp	A	F, vfi	Undulating
	B ₁	10-40	10 YR 4/4 (dark yellowish brown)	g,cl	Mo,c,sab	N	III	d,b	m,fr; w,ssp	A	C, vfi	
	B ₂	40-90	7.5YR 4/6 (strong brown)	g,cl	wm,me,sab	N	III	d,b	m, lo,w,ssp	A	Vf,,vfi	
	Bv	90-133	2.5YR 5/6(red)	g,cl	Mo,me,ab	A, co,cl	II	d,s	m,lo;w,spl	A	F, vfi	

DESCRIPTION KEYS

Texture ++: b= boulder; s= stony; g= gravelly; cs= coarse sandy; fs= fine sandy; sl= silty; cl= clayey; l= loamy. **Structure** ++: we=weak; mo=moderate; st=strong; wm=weak to moderate; ms= medium to strong; c= coarse; f=fine; g=granular; cr=crumbs; sg= single grained; pl= platy; sab=sub-angular blocky; ab= angular blocky. **Mottles** +++: v= very small, me=medium. **Mottles** ++: n=none; v= very few; f=few; c=common; m=many; a=abundant; vf= very fine; md= medium; co=coarse; fa=faint; d=distinct; p=prominent; s= sharp; cl=clear; d=diffuse. **Consistence** *: m= moist; w=wet; fr= friable; fi=firm; st= strong; l=loose; c=crummy; sst= slightly sticky; spt=slightly plastic; s=sicky; p=plastic; nst= non-sticky; npl= non plastic, lo=loose, ssp=sticky and slightly plastic. **Boundary** **: c= clear; s= smooth; g= gradual; d= diffuse; w=wavy; di= breakage (Discontinuous). **Drainage** ***: I= swamp; II= poorly drained; III=well drained. **Artifacts** ^: P= Present; A= Absent. **Roots** ^v: V= Very few; F= Few; C= Common, M= Many; vfi= Very fine; fi= Fine; md= Medium; co= Coarse, A = Absent

Table 4. Physical and chemical properties of soil profile pit horizons

Soil	Hor	Depth	Silt	Clay	Sand	pH	pH (H ₂ O)	pH (KCl)	EC (µS cm ⁻¹)	Av. P (%)	C (%)	N (%)	EA	Ca	Na	Mg	K	ECEC	BS	
			(%)	(%)	(%)	(KCl)	(H ₂ O)	(KCl)	cm ⁻¹	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
UTRF 1	A	0-20	2.0	8.48	89.52	7.18	6.52	42.00	6.74	2.82	0.08	0.96	1.97	3.69	1.48	0.55	8.64	88.93		
	B ₁	20-40	2.0	8.48	89.52	7.44	6.28	80.00	6.82	2.78	0.01	0.48	4.75	3.37	2.15	0.89	11.64	95.88		
	B ₂	40-60	12.0	8.48	79.52	6.56	6.13	58.00	7.23	2.60	0.02	0.53	1.19	1.85	2.50	0.91	6.91	92.42		
UTRF 2	Bv	60-115	6.0	12.48	81.52	7.80	6.12	132.00	7.01	3.18	0.05	0.50	1.97	2.92	1.63	0.69	7.71	93.56		
	A	0-10	2.0	8.48	89.52	6.82	6.50	5.08	6.72	3.04	0.07	0.82	0.41	2.91	1.74	0.91	6.79	87.93		
UTRF 2	B ₁	10-40	12.0	10.48	77.52	6.80	6.77	18.00	7.28	2.89	0.07	0.06	1.56	3.19	1.92	1.06	8.33	92.80		
	B ₂	40-90	10.0	18.48	71.52	7.19	5.82	38.00	7.32	2.58	0.08	0.32	2.03	1.93	2.17	1.08	7.54	95.70		
	Bv	90-115	2.0	8.48	89.52	7.57	6.33	52.00	6.82	2.05	0.07	0.46	1.94	2.80	2.89	0.97	9.05	94.92		

EA: exchangeable acidity; BS: base saturation

Table 5. *Properties of biochar material*

pH (H ₂ O)	10.22
pH (KCl)	9.24
Electrical Conductivity (µS/cm)	5.08
Available Phosphorus (mg/kg)	5.59
Organic Carbon (%)	34.08
Nitrogen (%)	0.28
Ca (cmol/kg)	1.99
Na (cmol/kg)	0.30
Mg (cmol/kg)	1.55
K (cmol/kg)	2.10
ECEC (cmol/kg)	6.60
Ash content (%)	24.3
Moisture content (%)	4.21
Fixed carbon (%)	48.96
Volatile matter (%)	22.53

Field Experiment

The field experiment was conducted in the rainy season of 2019 (August – Nov.). It was laid out in a Complete Randomized Design (CRD) on each soil. Four treatments were used; control (C), NPK 20:10:10 at 600 kg/ha (NPK), biochar at 3.5 t/ha + NPK 20:10:10 at 600 kg/ha (biochar+NPK), and biochar at 3.5 t/ha (B). Treatments were replicated thrice on plots measuring 2 x 4 m (8 m²) and separated by a buffer of 1 m between plots. In NPK plots, 200 g was applied and 400 g at 6 weeks after planting. Biochar was applied after tillage, before planting, and control treatments were not treated with any amendment. Quality protein maize (QPM), a hybrid variety, was planted immediately after amendments. Seeds were sown at 2 seeds per hole, 25 cm within the row and 75 cm between row spacing. Hand weeding was done at 21 days, 6 and 9 weeks after planting (WAP). The second NPK split application was made at 6 (WAP)

Carbon Mineralisation Measurement

Soil respiration was measured in situ using the alkali absorption method, using the non-flow-through steady-state (static chamber) system (Hopkins, 2006). Field chambers were constructed using a PVC non-reactive material following the USDA Agricultural Research Service guidelines in Parkin and Venterea (2010). Permanent chambers (10.6 cm diameter Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) pipes of 30 cm height were installed to 20 cm depth) in the centre of each treatment plot at spots cleared of all organic matter residue. Three chambers were

used as blanks. Carbon dioxide emission was trapped in 60 mL plastic vials containing 40 mL 0.25 M NaOH. Five millilitres (5 mL) aliquots of the trapping solution (0.25 M NaOH) were back-titrated to a colourless end-point with 0.15 M HCl after precipitation of carbonates by adding 8 mL 3M BaCl₂ using phenolphthalein as an indicator (Haber, 1958). CO₂ was sampled on days 1, 3, 6 and every three days intervals till the maturity of the test crop.

CO₂-C was evaluated using the equation:

$$CO_2 - C = ((B - V) \times M \times E) / (A \times T)$$

Where:

CO₂- C = C efflux (mg m⁻² d⁻¹); B = volume of HCl solution used for the titration of treatment samples (mL); V = volume of HCl solution used for the titration of blank samples (mL);

M = molarity (mol L⁻¹) of the HCl solution; E = carbon gram-equivalent (6 g);

A = exposed soil surface area (m²); and T = sampling time (d).

Meteorological Data

Rainfall (total rainfall between gas sampling times) and soil temperature (mean 0-20 cm) data was obtained from the University of Ilorin Teaching and Research Farm Meteorological station. The meteorological station is 1.6 and 0.4 km away from UTRF 1 and 2 respectively.

Data Analysis

Data collected on C mineralisation was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $p = 0.05$. In contrast, rainfall, soil temperature and carbon mineralisation data were subjected to Pearson Correlation (r) analysis to explore the relationships between the variables. Calculations were done in SPSS 20th Edition.

Results and Discussion

Variation in C Mineralization and CO₂ Emission Treatments and Soils

Table 6 shows the results of the analyses of variance of means of experimental factors. The highest CO₂ emissions were recorded under NPK treatment (79.856 mg), while the least was in the biochar alone treatment at 74.845 mg. However, the differences in the values for all treatments were not significant at $p \leq 0.05$. CO₂ emission rate followed a similar trend with that of total emissions, having no significant difference among treatment applications. Soils, however, exerted significant variations both in total CO₂ emission and emission rate. The highest values were recorded in UTRF 2, with observations of 82.351 mg and 1.183 mg m⁻² d⁻¹ for total CO₂ emission and mean emission rates, respectively. These values were significantly higher than those recorded in UTRF 1 at $p \leq 0.01$ and $p \leq 0.05$, respectively. No significant interactions were recorded between experimental factors.

The observations recorded showed that sole NPK treatment and that incorporated with biochar resulted in higher C mineralisation. This observation is different from the findings of Olaniyan et al. (2020) in their evaluation of biochar C stability in soils around the same geographical location as in this study. In their research, they found that SOC and biochar C mineralisation was lower in soils of higher organic N, and they attributed their finding to the possible toxicity effect of high N on soil C degradation microbial communities. However, the N contents of the soils in the study are much higher than those in this research. This may explain the variation observed. At lower soil N levels, N addition may increase microbial population and activities rather than inhibit it, which will result in higher N mineralisation.

The finding also differs from that of Perveen et al. (2019) but is consistent with that of Wang et al. (2015), which reported that N enrichment resulted in higher CO₂ release in croplands. The variation in C mineralisation responses between soils can be attributed to differences in properties. While both soils are comparable in properties, especially soil physical (particle size fractions) with a similar range in sand silt and clay components, UTRF 1 had a higher OC amount. This can be attributed to the propensity of low OC soils to better adsorb soil C on soil clay mineral surfaces, which makes it less free for microbial degradation. Kimetu et al. (2009) also reported that amended C is less accessible for microbial utilisation in low N and C soils.

Table 6. Variation in means of CO₂ emissions in treatments and soils

	Total CO ₂ emission (mg)	Mean CO ₂ emission rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Treatment		
B	74.845	1.072
Biochar+NPK (BN)	78.964	1.134
C	77.494	1.125
NPK	79.856	1.157
<i>F-value</i>	0.512	0.696
<i>p-value</i>	0.680 NS	0.568 NS
Soil		
UTRF 1	73.228	1.061
UTRF 2	82.351	1.183
<i>F-value</i>	8.870	7.828
<i>p-value</i>	0.009 **	0.013 *
Interaction		
T x S	0.510 NS	0.382 NS

*: significant at $p \leq 0.05$, **: significant at $p \leq 0.01$, NS: not significant

Relationship Between Soil Temperature and C Mineralization in Soils and Treatments

Fig. 2 shows topsoil (0 – 20 cm) temperature and CO₂ emission rate trends in treatments and soils. There was no clear trend in C mineralisation and emissions in both soils with soil temperature. The general direction was highly fluctuating emission rates at the start of incubation before a stabilisation at about day 45 and 57 in UTRF 1 and 2, respectively. This observation largely conforms with previous findings of a more variable emission at the start of incubation and a steady progression with time (El-Naggar et al., 2015; Olaniyan et al., 2020).

However, correlation analyses showed that the relationship between soil temperature and C mineralisation differed between treatments and soils. In Table 7, which presents the results of correlation analysis on an individual soil basis, there was a significant positive relationship between soil temperature and SOC mineralisation under biochar (B) treatment ($r=0.44$; $p=0.03$; $N=24$) in UTRF 2, whereas the relationship was not significant in UTRF 1,

and the correlation was negative. No other correlation for the different treatments was substantial.

A general correlation analysis (Table 8) irrespective of soils also showed that soil temperature had a significant positive correlation with C mineralisation rate under biochar treatment ($r=0.29$; $p=0.04$; $N=24$), and the same observation as in the soil-wise analysis was observed, with no significant correlation under other treatments. Although insignificant, the relationship between soil temperature and C mineralisation was positive under all experimental treatments. This finding aligns with that of Benbi and Khosa (2014), in who they found that incubation medium temperature significantly influenced C mineralisation. Although they also noted that the chemical composition of the C source also determines how much effect temperature has on C mineralisation. This also applies in the current study. The variation in inherent C sources in the soils can be attributed to the difference in the relationships observed between soil temperature and C mineralisation in the two soils.

Fig. 2. Soil temperature and CO₂ emission rate trends in soils and treatments

Table 7. *CO₂ emission rate, rainfall and soil temperature relationships in soils and treatments*

Soil	Treatment		Rainfall (mm)	Top (20 cm) Soil Temp (°C)
	Emission Rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)			
UTRF 1	NPK	r	-.080	.040
		P	.711	.853
	C	r	.144	.059
		p	.503	.784
	BN	r	.110	.118
		P	.610	.582
	B	r	-.100	-.017
		P	.642	.939
UTRF 2	NPK	r	.170	.295
		P	.427	.161
	C	r	-.055	.287
		P	.797	.174
	BN	r	.323	.238
		P	.123	.263
	B	r	.211	.444*
		P	.323	.030

N=24, *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), CN: control treatment; B: biochar treatment; NPK: NPK treatment; BN: biochar-NPK treatment

Table 8. *General CO₂ emission rate, rainfall and soil temperature relationships in experimental treatments*

Treatment		Top (20 cm) Soil Temp (°C)	Rainfall (mm)
B Emm rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	R	0.289*	0.096
	P	0.046	0.516
BN Emm rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	R	0.264	0.224
	P	0.070	0.127
C Emm rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	R	0.216	0.058
	P	0.140	0.698
NPK Emm rate (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	R	0.261	0.081
	P	0.074	0.586

N=24, *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), CN: control treatment; B: biochar treatment; NPK: NPK treatment; BN: biochar-NPK treatment

Relationship Between Soil Moisture and C Mineralization in Soils and Treatments

Fig. 3 shows the trends of soil moisture and C mineralisation in this study. As with soil temperature, there was no strong consonance between soil moisture and C mineralisation fluctuations. This is reinforced by the correlation analysis carried out. The results showed that rainfall amount had no significant correlation with C mineralisation and CO₂ emissions under treatments in both soils. Also, the direction of relationships differed slightly between treatments, with NPK and B treatments having a weak negative correlation in UTRF 1 and the control (C) treatment in UTRF 2.

Fig. 3. Rainfall trend and treatments CO₂ emission rates in soils and treatments

This finding supports models that have shown that C mineralisation declines under elevated moisture. In their study, Benbi and Khosa (2014) found that the flooding of experimental soils reduced the mineralisation of added C. In a separate study, Huang and Hall (2017) reported an initial (25 days) suppression of C mineralisation, following water saturation above field capacity. However, after this initial period, they reported that elevated moisture stimulated cumulative CO₂ and CH₄ losses up to over 150 % compared to the

control. Stable C isotopes examination in their study showed that C losses were derived from C₃-C release under Fe reduction at high soil moistures.

The observations in this study suggest that soil C losses with soil water may be more connected to the leaching DOC. Studies have shown that moisture-induced high C mineralisation results in moisture levels that optimise soil oxygen supply and carbon substrate diffusion (Linn and Doran, 1984). As this study was carried out during peak rainfall in the study area, which results in high water saturation above field capacity, the saturating may have resulted in the C mineralisation observations recorded.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In examining the influence of soil management, temperature and moisture on C mineralisation in this study, the finding showed that assessed management options did not significantly affect C mineralisation. However, the two soils evaluated differed in C mineralisation responses. This observation could be attributed to a variation in soil properties, most likely OC, since the soils were mainly similar in other properties except in OC gradient. Findings showed that C mineralisation is more sensitive to soil temperature under sole biochar treatment. Although this observation did not cut across both soils studied individually, analyses showed that higher temperatures increased C mineralisation under exclusive biochar treatment. The outcome of this study can be applied in timing biochar application to the soil to maximise its carbon sequestration potential.

Declaration of competing interest: The authors declare that there are no competing interests in the publication of this paper.

Acknowledgements: The contribution of all authors is acknowledged

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Data Statement: The corresponding author's research is available upon reasonable request.

References

- Ajadi, B.S., Adeniyi, A., Afolabi, M.T. (2011). Impact of climate on urban agriculture: Case study of Ilorin City, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, 11(1), 24-29.
- American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard. (2009). Standard test method for chemical analysis of wood charcoal. Conshohocken, PA: American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) International.
- Benbi, D.K., Khosa, M.K. (2014). Effects of Temperature, Moisture, and Chemical Composition of Organic Substrates on C Mineralization in Soils. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 45 (21) 2734-2753, DOI: 10.1080/00103624.2014.950423
- Blake, G.R., Hartage, K.H. (1986). Bulk Density, in: Klute, A. (Eds), *Methods of soil analysis part 1*, Madison, Wisconsin: American Society of Agronomy No. 9. pp. 365-375.
- Bray, R.H., Kurtz, L.T. (1945). Soil determination of total organic and available form of phosphate in soils. *Soil Science*, 59, 225-229. DOI:10.1097/00010694-194501000-00006
- Bremner, J.M. (1960). Determination of nitrogen in soil by the Kjeldahl method. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 55, 11-31. DOI: 10.1017/S0021859600021572

Ding, X., Yuan, Y., Liang, Y., Li, L. and Han, X. (2014). Impact of long-term application of manure, crop residue, and mineral fertiliser on organic carbon pools and crop yields in a Mollisol. *Journal of Soils Sediments*, 14, 854–859.

El-Naggar, A., Lee, S.S., Awad, Y.M., Yang, X., Ryu, C., Rizwan, M., Rinklebe, J., Tsang, D.C.W. and Ok, Y.S. (2018). Influence of soil properties and feedstocks on biochar potential for carbon mineralisation and improvement of infertile soils. *Geoderma*, 332, 100–108. DOI:10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.06.017

Enders, A. and Lehmann, J. (2012). Comparison of wet digestion and dry-ashing methods for total elemental analysis of biochar. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 43, 1042–1052. DOI: 10.1080/00103624.2012.656167

Gee, W.G., Or, D. (2002). Particle-size analysis, in: Dane, J., Topp, G.C. (Eds.), *Methods of Soil Analysis*, Book series: 5. Part 4. Soil Science Society of America, USA, pp 255–293.

Guo, N., Shi, X., Zhao, Y., Xu, S., Wang, M., Zhang, G., Wu, J., Huang, B., Kong, C. (2017). Environmental and anthropogenic factors driving changes in paddy soil organic matter: A case study in the middle and lower Yangtze River Plain of China. *Pedosphere*, 27, 926–937.

Haber, W. (1958). Ecological analysis of soil respiration (review of methods). *Flora*, 146, 109–157.

Hackl, E., Pfeffer, M., Dona, C., Bachmann, G., Zechmeister-Boltenstern, S. (2005). Composition of the microbial communities in the mineral soil under different types of natural forest. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*, 37, 661–671. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2004.08.023

Herold, N., Schoening, I., Michalzik, B., Trumbore, S., Schrumpf, M. (2014). Controls on soil carbon storage and turnover in German landscapes. *Biogeochemistry*, 119, 435–451. DOI: 10.1007/s10533-014-9978-x

Hopkins, D.W. (2006). Carbon Mineralisation, in: Carter, M.R. & Gregorich, E.G. (Eds.), *Soil sampling and methods of analysis*. Boca Raton, FL 33487-2742: Taylor & Francis Group, LLC. pp. 589–598.

Huang, W., Hall, S.J. (2017). Elevated moisture stimulates carbon loss from mineral soils by releasing protected organic matter. *Nature Communications*, 8, 1774. DOI:10.1038/s41467-017-01998-z

Jamala, G.Y. and Oke, D.O. (2013). Soil organic carbon fractions as affected by land use in the Southern Guinea Savanna Ecosystem of Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Science and Environmental Management*, 4(6), 116–122.

Juo, A.R., Ayanlaja, S.A., Ogunwale, J.A. (1976). An evaluation of cation exchange capacity measurements for soils in the tropics. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 7, 751–761. DOI: 10.1080/00103627609366684

Kimetu, J.M., Lehmann, J., Kinyangi, J.M., Cheng, C.H., Thies, J., Mugendi, D.N., Pell, A. (2009). Soil organic C stabilisation and thresholds in C saturation. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*, 41, 2100–2104. DOI:10.1016/j.soilbio.2009.07.022

Linn, D.M., Doran, J.W. (1984). Effect of water-filled pore space on carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide production in tilled and non-tilled soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 48, 1267–1272. DOI: 10.1023/A:1015062304915

Olaniyan, J.O., Isimikalu, T.O., Raji, B.A., Affinnih, K.O., Alasinrin, S.Y. and Ajala, O.N. (2020). An investigation of the effect of biochar application rates on CO₂ emissions in

soils under upland rice production in southern Guinea savannah of Nigeria. *Heliyon*. 6 (11), E05578, ISSN 2405-8440, DOI:10.1016/J.Heliyon.2020.E05578

Olaniyan, J.O., Ogunkunle., A.O. (2007). An evaluation of the soil map of Nigeria: II. Purity of mapping unit. *World Association of Soil and Water Conservation Journal*, 2, 97-108.

Parkin, T.B., Venterea, R.T. (2010). Chamber-Based Trace Gas Flux Measurements, in: Follet, RF (Eds.), *Sampling Protocols*. USDA-ARS. Pp 1-39. www.ars.usda.gov/research/GRACEnet

Peech, M., Cowan, R., Baker, G. (1962). A critical study of the BaCl₂-triethanolamine and the Ammonium acetate methods for determining the exchangeable hydrogen content of soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 26, 37-40. DOI:10.2136/sssaj1962.03615995002600010010x

Perveen, N., Ayub, M., Shahzad, T., Siddiq, M.R., Memon, M.S., Barot, S., Saeed, H., Xu, M. (2019). Soil carbon mineralisation in response to nitrogen enrichment in surface and subsurface layers in two land use types. *PeerJ*, 7, e7130, DOI:10.7717/peerj.7130

Renner, R. (2007). Rethinking biochar. *Environmental Science Technology*, 41, 5932-5933. PMID: 17937262, DOI: 10.1021/es0726097

Trivedi, P., Singh, B.P., Singh, B.K. (2018). Soil Carbon: Introduction, Importance, Status, Threat, and Mitigation, in: Singh, B.K., (Eds), *Soil Carbon Storage*. Academic Press, pp 1-28. ISBN 9780128127667, DOI:10.1016/B978-0-12-812766-7.00001-9

United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Soil Science Division Staff. (2017). *Soil survey manual (Handbook 18 ed.)*. (C. Ditzler, K. Scheffe, & H. C. Monger, Eds.) Washington, DC: Government Printing Office.

United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (2014). *Soil Survey Field and Laboratory Methods Manual*. Soil Survey Investigations Report No. 51 Version 2. (R. Burt, & S. S. Staff, Eds.) Lincoln, Nebraska: US Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service.

VandenBygaart, A.J., Gregorich, E.G. and Angers, D.A. (2003). Influence of agricultural management on soil organic carbon: a compendium and assessment of Canadian studies. *Canadian Journal of Soil Science*, 83, 363-380.

Walkley, A., Black, T. A. (1934). Organic matter determination. *Soil Science*, 37, 29-38.

Wang, Y., Cheng, S., Fang, H., Yu, G., Xu, X., Xu, M., Wang, L., Li, X., Si, G., Geng, J., He, S. (2015). Contrasting effects of ammonium and nitrate inputs on soil CO₂ emission in a subtropical coniferous plantation of southern China. *Biology & Fertility of Soils*, 51, 815-825. DOI: 10.1007/s00374-015-1028-x

Xiao, S., Wei, Z. and Kelin, W. (2017). Soil aggregate mediates the impact of land uses on organic carbon, total nitrogen and microbial activity in a karst ecosystem. *Soil Biology Biochemistry*, 21, 206-213.